

**DESIGN OF A SLOPE MATCHED SINGLE MODE HIGHLY
BIREFRINGENT DISPERSION COMPENSATING HYBRID
PHOTONIC CRYSTAL FIBER**

**A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the
requirements for the degree of**

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in

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by

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to the

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Evaluation of the Thesis Work

Design of a Slope Matched Single Mode Highly Birefringent Dispersion Compensating Hybrid Photonic Crystal Fiber

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Abstract

Recent advances in Photonic Crystal Fiber (PCF) research have had a significant impact on optical fiber communication systems. The versatile applications of PCFs in the field of telecommunication and biomedical applications are now at the pinnacle. This thesis demonstrates the best potential design for hybrid photonic crystal fibers (HyPCF-I and II) with high birefringence established on modified broadband dispersion compensatory structure through E, S, C, and L communication bands, i.e. 1360 nm to 1625 nm wavelength. The main goal of this thesis is to design efficient hybrid photonic crystal fiber which can be used in sensing application and high bit rate communication with low loss. The justification of using the hybrid structure is also discussed in this research work. The key optical parameters of the proposed hybrid PCF structures are also compared with a simple hexagonal PCF structure. For high bit rate transmission through a long distance of an optical waveguide is dependent on the reduction of residual dispersion and residual dispersion slope matching with a single mode fiber. The residual dispersion slope matching and single mode performance by HOMER (Higher Order Mode Extinction Ratio) method is also evaluated in this thesis work. The hybrid PCF structures HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II demonstrates high birefringence 3.039×10^{-2} and 2.372×10^{-2} at 1550 nm respectively which is higher than the simple hexagonal PCF structure. At 1550 nm wavelength, the y polarization dispersion coefficient of HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II is -358.4 and -3534 ps/(nm.km) respectively. For single mode performance analysis the residual slope (RDS) matching for HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II is of 0.0036 nm^{-1} and 0.0034 nm^{-1} respectively at 1550 nm. Also the highest HOMER value at 1550 nm operating wavelength for HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II is found to be 10^6 and 10^4 . Moreover, the performance parameters and optical properties are compared with some existing designs.

Publications

Journal

- [1] Halder, A. and Anower, M.S., 2019. Relative dispersion slope matched highly birefringent and highly nonlinear dispersion compensating hybrid photonic crystal fiber. *Photonics and Nanostructures-Fundamentals and Applications*, 35, p.100704.
- [2] Halder, A., 2020. Slope matched highly birefringent hybrid dispersion compensating fiber over telecommunication bands with low confinement loss. *Journal of Optics*, 49(2), pp.187-195.

Conferences

- [1] A. Halder, "Highly birefringent photonic crystal fiber for dispersion compensation over E+S+C+L communication bands," 2016 5th International Conference on Informatics, Electronics and Vision (ICIEV), 2016, pp. 1099-1103, doi: 10.1109/ICIEV.2016.7760169.

List of Acronyms

Acronyms	Descriptions
DCF	Dispersion Compensation Fiber
FEM	Finite Element Method
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
HyPCF	Hybrid Photonic Crystal Fiber
HOF	Holey Optical Fiber
HNL	Highly Nonlinear
HNA	High Numerical Aperture
IG-PCF	Index Guiding Photonic Crystal Fiber
MOF	Micro structured Optical Fiber
PDE	Partial Differential Equation
PBG	Photonic Band Gap
RI	Refractive Index
SMF	Single Mode Fiber
TIR	Total Internal Reflection
WDM	Wavelength Division Multiplication

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Optical fibers evolved from conventional step index fibers to single material fibers with effective air cladding structures that demarcated propagation in the 1970s. Overall, systematic arranged fibers, such as photonic crystal fibers, are constituted of a cross-section (typically unvarying end to end the fiber length) microstructure of a single to multiple materials, most commonly arranged intermittently over a significant portion of the cross-section, typically as a "cladding" adjacent to a core (or several cores) where the light is confined.

PCF is an innovative type of optical fiber based on the properties of photonic crystals, which motivates researchers in the field of optics and photonics. Because of its ability to confine light in hollow cores or with confinement characteristics not possible in conventional optical fiber, PCF is now finding applications in fiber-optic communications, fiber lasers, nonlinear devices, high-power transmission, highly sensitive gas sensors, and other areas. More specific categories of PCF include photonic band gap fiber (PCFs that confine light by band gap effects), holey fiber (PCFs using air holes in their cross-sections), hole-assisted fiber (PCFs guiding light by a conventional higher-index core modified by the presence of air holes), and Bragg fiber (photonic bandgap fiber formed by concentric rings of multilayer film). Photonic crystal fibers may be considered a subgroup of a more general class of microstructure optical fibers, where light is guided by structural modifications, and not only by refractive index differences.

When PCF (Photonic Crystal Fiber) was invented, it marked a significant milestone in fiber history. It holds a great deal of promise and potential. The wider design space, flexible, outstanding, and remarkable optical qualities are considered the key to countless scientific and technological applications in both linear and nonlinear regimes. PCFs and how we explore their potential in light mastery are thought to be the future of optics. The health-care industry, for example, needs new wavelength lasers or broadband light sources for diagnosis, while the telecommunications industry needs more flexible amplifiers and

low-cost fibers, and the sensor industry needs environmental sensors and sensitive gas detector systems for both local and remote sensing. PCFs can be used as optical components in any of these new industries, whether hollow core or solid core. Damage thresholds are higher than in standard fibers, allowing them to deliver high-power laser beams for cutting and welding. They have a great deal of potential for a variety of nonlinear optical processes that are important for environmental sensing. Some developing applications, such as power delivery, ultra-short pulse delivery, and pulse compression, require the refinement and design of additional properties such as enhanced bandwidth, near-zero flat chromatic dispersion, and nonlinear response control. These vital jobs continue to face significant technological challenges. Some of these difficulties will be addressed briefly in the following sections, and in greater depth in the following chapters.

Due to the flexibility to design and the optical properties could be managed through design it is a great motivation for me to design the photonic crystal fiber waveguides. By designing different structures we could be able to achieve our desired enhancement in optical fiber communication. Throughout the world now the designs are realizable and significant effects in biomedical sector are now booming. In this context the basic improvements and also performance parameters should be developed. So, continuous research and new innovations also developing the designs are also important in this field. Given the seemingly limitless potential of this expanding field and the aforementioned technological issues, I have decided to join the ongoing efforts to design smart PCFs for a variety of technological applications.

1.2 Background

The photonic crystal fiber is a kind of optical fiber in which the cladding around the core of the cable is made of photonic crystals. An irregular array of microscopic air holes running the length of the fiber creates a low loss periodic dielectric medium. The goal of photonic band gaps technique is to prevent light from propagating in specific directions at specific wavelengths. Photonic crystal fibers as compared to traditional fiber optics use total internal reflection or light captivity to propagate light.

Figure 1.1 Transverse section view of photonic crystal fiber. [46]

The concept of placing distinct periodic geometrical air hole patterns along the fiber cladding on a silica foundation to provide variable optical properties is known as photonic crystal fiber (PCF) [1]. PCFs, or micro-structured optical fibers, are widely used in sensing, dispersion compensation, nonlinear optical applications, and high-bit-rate data transmission. Dispersion is a major issue in wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) and high bit rate transmission systems because it broadens the optical pulse while limiting the system's bandwidth. In high-speed WDM systems, compensation for transmission qualities such as dispersion and slope of single mode fiber (SMF) is critical [2]. At 1550 nm, the negative dispersion coefficient for standard dispersion compensating fiber is around -100 to -300 ps/(nm.km) [3]. This type of fiber also has a high rate of loss. Since it is introduced to reduce losses and expenses, the dispersion compensating fiber (DCF) should be as short as possible with high negative dispersion [4]-[8]. The flexibility in dispersion regulation is addressed by photonic crystal fiber (PCF) or holey fiber. Variation in the size and position of air-holes can influence the dispersive properties, which is important for dispersion compensation in fiber design [9]-[10]. Birefringence is a polarization-maintaining fiber's feature that makes it appropriate for optical sensing applications. When the fiber core is made asymmetric by engaging deliberate manufactured faults at the center core, or the air pores are made elliptical rather than circular, high birefringence can be attained on a PCF structure [11]. To address the fabrication challenge, employing circular air holes to achieve high birefringence provides a benefit over elliptical ones. Circular air holes, rather than elliptical air holes, are easier to make. Researchers have proposed many

sorts of PCF designs in recent years in order to address diverse applications such as high birefringence and dispersion compensation.

1.3 Literature Review

In recent years, optical fiber has become an important component of the information superhighway. Probably the most significant technological breakthrough in recent telecom history has been the development of optical fibers. It has steadily supplanted copper cable and satellite connectivity in telecom networks due to its numerous appealing qualities. The use of fiber optic connections enables signal transmission over greater distances and at faster data rates than traditional communication methods. Fibers used in telecommunications systems have lower attenuation and are less susceptible to electromagnetic interference. Fibers are commonly used in non-telecom systems as well as telecom applications. It is becoming increasingly appealing for remote sensing, medical imaging, illuminations, machining, and welding applications due to its smaller size, lower weight, chemical inertness, higher bandwidth, longer repeater span, electromagnetic immunity, and many other exciting qualities.

Optical fibers are typically made of two glasses and are used to transmit light signals. It's a cylindrical waveguide with a higher refractive index solid glass core that runs down the center of the fiber. The core is surrounded by a homogeneous cladding of another solid glass with a lower refractive index. The two glasses are made of silica, which is a common material (SiO_2). Most of the time, germanium or fluorine is doped with silica to increase or decrease the refractive index of the silica glass. An index difference between the core and the cladding helps trap light inside the core and guide it along the length of the fiber by using the complete internal reflection mechanism (TIR). This type of optical fiber is referred to as "conventional optical fiber." Despite the fact that such fibers have a wide range of applications in both telecom and non-telecom applications, they cannot do everything. The properties of the glass used to make such conventional fibers are the limiting factor. Due to the rigidity of silica glass, ordinary fibers are incompatible with certain new applications. Because conventional fibers are difficult to produce, another potential breakthrough in fiber-optics technology, the photonic crystal fiber (PCF), also known as the holey optical fiber (HOF) or the microstructure optical fiber, has been developed (MOF).

Researchers have recently proposed numerous types of PCF designs to address diverse applications such as high birefringence and dispersion compensation. The octagonal-shaped photonic crystal fiber recommended in [12] has a strong negative dispersion coefficient of -588 ps/(nm.km) and a birefringence value of 1.81×10^{-2} . The reported negative dispersion coefficient is -239.51 ps/(nm.km) in another octagonal shape, and the birefringence is 1.67×10^{-2} [13]. A spiral design with a birefringence of 1.6×10^{-2} and a negative dispersion coefficient of -400 ps/(nm.km) was proposed previously [14]. In 2016, it was proposed that a defective core PCF with four elliptical air holes near the central core achieve high birefringence of 3.373×10^{-2} and high negative dispersion of -837.8 ps/(nm.km) over E to L communication bands [15]. Fabrication of the fiber was complicated due to the utilization of elliptical air pores. Furthermore, employing a defective core circular PCF, some recent works have shown a birefringence of 2.75×10^{-2} and a negative dispersion of -331 ps/(nm.km) at 1550nm operating wavelength spanning S+C+L bands [16]. A PCF with negative dispersion of -134 to -385 ps/(nm.km) and birefringence of 2.13×10^{-2} was reported in 2014 [17]. It covered the E to U bands and had a negative dispersion of -134 to -385 ps/(nm.km). In the same year, a decagonal PCF with negative dispersion of -390 ps/(nm.km) was specified [18]. Kim et al. presented a defective core PCF with elliptical air hole with a negative flattened dispersion of -156.05 ps/(nm.km) and a birefringence of 1.94×10^{-2} in 2011 [19]. The construction of the proposed design includes all elliptical air openings. In 2016, Ali et al. suggested a PCF for high birefringence of 2.78×10^{-2} with a negative dispersion of -345 ps/(nm.km) based on a circular cladding with asymmetric core [20].

1.4 Objectives

The main objective of this thesis is to design efficient hybrid photonic crystal fiber that can-

- Increase the birefringence.
- Match the slope with single mode fiber.
- Enhance the single mode performance.
- Reduce the confinement loss.
- Attain higher nonlinear coefficient.
- Achieve high bit rate transmission by dispersion compensation in the communication band for WDM communication.

1.5 Justification for the research

The introduction of Photonic Crystal Fibers and their many design processes in recent years has shown some incredible light characteristics. It is now employed in spectrometry, sensing, and biological applications, as well as in optical communication medium, in the field of photonics and light wave technology. In long-distance optical communication, the property of single mode operation in optical fiber is extremely useful. This fiber's additive features include birefringence and nonlinearity with low loss. Because the suggested fiber has a dual property, it can be employed successfully for both sensing and telecommunication purposes.

1.6 Thesis Organization

Chapter 1 discussed the motivation behind the research and study, background of the advent of photonic crystal fiber, literature review of different articles, specific objectives to be obtained, justification for the research and also the chronology of the chapters.

Chapter 2 exposed a brief on photonic crystal fibers, classification of PCFs, light guiding mechanisms, mode of operations, fabrication technologies and lastly the modal properties of PCF which is going to lead the performance attributes of the hybrid PCFs.

Chapter 3 contrasted a brief review of the research methodology, numerical method, brief on finite element method and design procedure with fabrications of the proposed PCFs. This chapter represents the base which lays the thesis work.

Chapter 4 contains the simulation results and its analysis. The performance parameters has been obtained and also compared with the existing research articles and previous proposed designs.

Finally the chapter 5 highlighted the conclusion and future scope of this kind of fiber designs in brief.

Chapter 2

Fundamentals of Photonic Crystal Fiber Design

2.1 Photonic Crystal Fiber

Optical fibers have evolved into a variety of shapes since their practical breakthroughs in the 1970s as traditional step index fibers and later as single material fibers with an effective air cladding structure. Regular structured fibers, such as photonic crystal fibers, have a crosssection microstructured from one, two, or more materials, which are most commonly organized periodically over much of the cross-section, usually as a "cladding" surrounding a core (or multiple cores) where light is confined.

According to Eli Yablonovitch [43], certain three-dimensionally periodic photonic crystal formations have entire photonic band gaps. The presence of these band gaps indicated that no propagating modes were present in the material over a specific frequency range. This means that if it were used as a cladding material, the signal would be unable to travel into and through it. This prediction heralded the possibility of developing a core-cladding contact with total internal reflection in the realm of fiber optic production.

However, the required interface behavior necessitates the correct refractive index contrast, pitch, and structural integrity, making the fabrication of these three-dimensionally periodic crystal structures very challenging. The answer was to design a two-dimensionally periodic material that is constant along its length and periodic in the plane orthogonal to the fiber's axis. By embedding tiny holes parallel to the core axis along the length of the cladding, as shown in Figure 2.1, this innovative fiber production approach produces an optically excellent approximation of this 2-D structure. The new cladding material's birefringent nature can be changed by modifying the size, spacing, and pattern of the holes, and the optical characteristics of the material are highly engineerable. It is possible to achieve a refractive index contrast between the core and cladding that is two orders of magnitude greater than that of ordinary fibers.

Figure 2.1 Cross Section of Photonic Crystal Fiber. [47]

Figure 2.2 exhibits the different hole arrangement patterns of photonic crystal fibers.

Figure 2.2 Two different hole arrangement pattern of (a) solid core index guiding and (b) hollow core band gap guiding PCF. [48]

The power-handling capacity of such fibers will be many orders of magnitude greater than that of conventional fibers since the maximum intensity in silica is at least two orders of magnitude lower than the peak intensity. Silica's nonlinear response in conventional fibers will result in fewer interactions overall. The dispersion of fibers is unaffected by the dispersion of silica as a material for the same reason. These fiber's limitations are still a mystery.

2.2 Conventional Optical Fiber versus PCF

For doped silica fibers, the difference in refractive index between the core and cladding is often only a few percent. The core has a greater refractive index than the cladding. The core's refractive index is increased above that of the silica cladding by doping a high refractive index material in the core region. Fluorine is a frequent ingredient for decreasing the refractive index, whereas germanium is a frequent compound for increasing it.

Figure 2.3 Schematic cross sections and index-profiles of (a) IG-PCFs (the dotted circle in the center indicates an omitted air-hole) and (b) PBG-PCFs (the larger circle in the center represents the core).

Figure 2.4 Schematic cross sections and index-profiles of (a) PCFs (a missing air-hole in the center represents the core) and (b) Ordinary fibers.

As previously mentioned, the PCF is a single material fiber with microscopic air holes in a silica background. The two types of fibers are shown in Figure 2.4. The index difference between the core and cladding is rather minor in traditional fibers, but it is large and controllable in PCFs by adjusting the cladding parameters. The fundamental distinction between the two fibers, which has a considerable impact on their optical properties. Among other properties, the latter shows extremely high or low nonlinearities, high birefringence, flat-dispersion, and wider single-mode functioning.

2.3 Light Guiding Mechanism of PCF

PCFs are guided by light using the TIR and PBG processes, respectively [21]. If the PCF uses the TIR mechanism to guide light, it is referred to as an IG-PCF or an HIC-PCF. If the light guidance is based on the PBG mechanism, it is sometimes referred to as a PBG-PCF, LIC-PCF, or HC-PCF. Figure 2.3(a) demonstrates that IG-PCFs frequently lack even a single air-hole. This kind of PCF can also use a doped core made of a high index material, like Ge. In any case, the refractive index of the core must be greater than that of the cladding ($n_{co} > n_{cl}$). Contrary to IG-PCFs, PBG PCFs have a hollow core ($n_{co} < n_{cl}$), which is often created by enlarging the air hole in the middle, as shown in Figure 2.3. (b).

2.4 Different Classes of PCF

Future classifications of PCFs [22] based on fiber qualities, topologies, and specialized guiding features could include a number of other types. The three different types of IG-PCFs are high numerical aperture (HNA) fibers, which have large core dimensions and small refractive index contrasts to allow spreading out of the guiding light to provide a larger effective area, LMA fibers, which have larger core dimensions and small refractive index contrasts to allow spreading out of the guiding light to provide a larger effective area, and HNL fibers, which have very small core dimensions to provide tight mode confinement (having a microstructure cladding surrounded by a ring of air-holes with larger dimensions). Additionally, hole assisted PCFs are IG-PCFs that have a holey coating and a doped core (high index material doped silica) (HA-PCFs). PBG-PCFs come in three different varieties: LIC fibers, Bragg fibers, and air-guiding (AG)/HC fibers. Figure 2.5 shows every type of microstructure fiber available.

Polarization maintenance (PM) fibers are a different class of PCF that have an asymmetric cladding structure or a stress-applying region to sustain linear polarization. Similar to

conventional fibers, PCFs are classified as single mode or multi-mode fibers based on how many modes they can support (IG or PBG).

Figure 2.5 Classification of the different types of photonic crystal fibers.

2.5 Evolution of the PCF Research Field

The field of PCF study was established when Knight et al. presented the initial demonstration of a holey optical fiber in 1996. They have demonstrated how to realistically construct a fiber with periodic air-holes that is laid out in a hexagonal lattice. They found that the unique holey fiber is similar to regular fibers in that it guides light via a modified TIR mechanism, despite their initial goal of identifying light guiding based on the PBG notion. They soon learned that the innovative fabric is strong and good at steering light. Light may be incorporated into it very easily. Traditional fibers and PCFs differed significantly in terms of design space and optical properties.

As a result, the area of index guiding PCFs is developing. However, hollow core fibers were not initially achieved since it was difficult to obtain large air holes for fiber cores in the required dimension, which is essential for PBG guidance. The PBG was finally shown in 1998 as a result of developments in numerical computation, including the development of full vector numerical methods. PCF research has advanced significantly since its discovery in 1996, as seen in Table 2.1.

Since then, it has been the focus of innumerable academic and industry research projects all over the world, developing into a significant area of electro-optical study.

2.6 Scope and Challenges of PCF Design

Despite all of the potentials and options, PCFs have application-specific design issues. To fully explore the benefits of PCF technology above conventional fibers, those application-specific design issues must be successfully resolved.

Table 2.1 PCF's Developmental Milestones

Year	Milestone
1996	First Index Guiding (Solid Core) PCF
1997	Endlessly Single Mode PCF
1998	Large Mode Area PCF
1999	Hollow Core PCF, Dispersion Shifted PCF
2000	Multicore PCF, PM PCF, Er-doped PCF Laser and Super-continuum
2001	Polymer PCF, Nonlinear processes in PCF
2002	SF6 Glass PCF
2003	Tellurite Glass PCF
2004	FWM twin Photon Generation in PCF, Ge-doped PCF
2005	PBGs at 1% index contrast, Bismuth PCF
2006	Gas and Liquid filled PCF
2008	Chalcogenide highly nonlinear PCF

2.7 Modes of Operation

Based on the way they confine light, photonic crystal fibers can operate in one of two ways. Although they can function using the same index-guiding principle as conventional optical fiber, those with solid cores or cores with higher average indices than the microstructure cladding can have much stronger confinement for use in nonlinear optical devices, polarization-maintaining fiber optics, and other applications. As an alternative, a "photonic band gap" fiber can be developed in which the microstructure cladding creates a photonic band gap that confines light. A correctly constructed band gap can contain light in a hollow core or even a core with a lower index. Hollow core band gap fibers may be able to get beyond some of the limits imposed by materials. The capacity to dynamically introduce materials into the core, such as a gas to be examined for the presence of a substance, is another possible advantage of a hollow core. Sol-gels with identical or

different index materials can be used to coat the holes in PCF to increase light transmission. Figure 2.6 shows the optical fiber's operational modes.

Figure 2.6 Modes of operation in optical fiber. [49]

2.8 PCF Fabrication

PCFs are made using fiber fibers. Several capillary silica rods and tubes are stacked together to form the required air-silica structure. This method, which has a lot of flexibility, helps with controlling the required level of precision in the structure. The silica-air structures that can be built using this versatile stack-and-draw technique are incredibly diverse. After building the desired performance, it is drawn using a conventional high-temperature drawing tower to hair-thin fiber dimensions. This technology makes it possible to fabricate extremely complex lattices by using the proper process control. The fibers are then covered with a shielding layer to prevent them from damage brought on by hard handling. The resulting fibers may be stripped and divided using standard methods, and they are strong and roughly the same size as regular fiber. Figure 2.7 illustrates the stack and draw method used to produce PCFs. Figure 2.8 illustrates a few created PCF samples.

Figure 2.7 Illustration of the versatile Stack-and-Draw fabrication method. [44]

Figure 2.8 Examples of some fabricated PCF. [45]

2.9 Modal Properties of PCF

This section discusses the modal features of PCFs that are relevant to the scope of this thesis. These features include chromatic dispersion, effective mode area, confinement loss, birefringence, nonlinear coefficient, single/multi-mode response, and splicing loss.

2.9.1 Chromatic Dispersion

Dispersion is a phenomena in optics that causes a wave to split into its spectral components. Separations of spectral components occur as a result of the wave's speed being proportional to its wavelength. To underscore its wavelength-dependent nature, it is sometimes referred to as the chromatic dispersion. The material dispersion, which results

from a frequency-dependent reaction of a material to waves, and the waveguide dispersion, which occurs when the speed of a wave through a waveguide relies on its operating frequency, are the two main origins of fiber dispersion.

Fiber dispersion causes signal deterioration in telecommunications. As seen in Figure 2.9, this is owing to the changing delay in arrival times between distinct components of a signal. Modal dispersion, which is generated by a waveguide having numerous modes at a given frequency, each with a different speed, is a comparable phenomena. The polarization mode dispersion (PMD) is a special case of this, which results from the superposition of two modes traveling at different speeds due to random flaws that break the waveguide's symmetry.

Figure 2.9 Figure illustrating dispersion phenomena in optical system. [50]

2.9.2 Effective Area

There are no tight cross-sectional boundaries in a beam of light that is steered through the core of an IG-PCF. The beam is strongest at the center of IG-core. PCF's From the core's center outward to the cladding region, the intensity of this light beam gradually decreases. A Gaussian distribution is a frequent model for beam intensity in single mode fibers. Equation (2.1) can be used to represent this Gaussian distribution, in which the current beam intensity is $I(r)$ between the radius r and the maximum beam intensity is $I(0)$ within radius $r = 0$, and the mode-field radius is w_r [26].

$$I(r) = I(0) \exp(-2r^2/w_r^2) \quad (2.1)$$

Figure 2.10 depicts the intensity distribution of a light beam within a fiber core region. Because it closely resembles the experimental profile, such a Gaussian distribution is frequently used to depict light dispersion in optical fibers [27-28].

Figure 2.10 Figure explaining mode field diameter and effective area of photonic crystal fiber (step index profile) [51].

$A_{eff}(\lambda)$ is the effective area where the light beam intensity drops to 13.5 percent of its highest value. The mode field diameter is the diameter that encompasses the effective area (MFD). The $A_{eff}(\lambda)$ and MFD can be calculated directly from the electric field distribution using the Petermann II formulation [34]. The effective area $A_{eff}(\lambda)$ is calculated using the equation (3.2), where \mathbf{E} is the electric field distribution calculated using Maxwell's equations [35]. Furthermore, the MFD can be determined using equation (2.3). In the following two equations, the corresponding effective area for the Gaussian field pattern ($E(x, y) = e^{-(x^2+y^2)/w_0^2}$), is $A_{eff}(\lambda) = \pi w_0^2$, where w_0 is the mode effective radius or the spot size, double of which is called the MFD.

$$A_{eff}(\lambda) = \frac{[\iint_{-\infty}^{\infty} (|E_x(x, y)|^2 + |E_y(x, y)|^2) dx dy]^2}{\iint_{-\infty}^{\infty} (|E_x(x, y)|^2 + |E_y(x, y)|^2)^2 dx dy} \quad (2.2)$$

$$MFD = 2 \sqrt{\frac{\int_0^{\infty} E(r)^2 r dr}{\int_0^{\infty} [dE(r)/dr]^2 r dr}} \quad (2.3)$$

2.9.3 Fiber Loss

Figure 2.11 depicts the optical loss spectrum of ordinary fibers. The loss spectrum of IG-PCFs is similar to that of conventional fibers in that it is dominated by the silica material. The following are the intrinsic optical losses of IG-PCFs:

$$\alpha [dB/km] = A_{sc}/\lambda^4 + B_{sc} + \alpha_{OH} + \alpha_{IR} \quad (2.4)$$

where, A_{sc} is the Rayleigh scattering coefficient, B_{sc} is the scattering loss owing to defects, α_{OH} is the OH absorption loss, and α_{IR} is the infrared absorption loss, and α is the overall optical loss.

Figure 2.11 Optical attenuation characteristics (loss versus wavelength) of silica fiber and the telecom windows [55].

Rayleigh scattering and IR losses are both intrinsic losses. The former is lower for pure silica fibers and higher in doped silica fibers, whereas the latter is only moderately affected by doping concentration, making PCFs equivalent to normal fibers. The loss of PCFs is largely determined by scattering due to defects and OH⁻ absorption losses. Imperfection losses in PCFs are caused by surface roughness, scratches, and contaminant depositions in the air holes. Such scattering losses can be reduced by using a high-precision production technique. The OH⁻ absorption losses can come from the silica glass itself or from the fabrication process itself. The OH⁻ absorption losses can be reduced by using high quality silica glass and an appropriate dehydration procedure.

2.9.4 Confinement Loss

Confinement loss occurs when a portion of the directed light penetrates the cladding zone, causing signal deterioration. IG-PCFs, like conventional fibers, guide light via the TIR mechanism and support three different modes. The guided mode, the radiation mode, and the leaky mode are the three modes [36]. Confinement loss is viewed as a loss of leaky modes in all of them. The effective refractive indices of the core and cladding are the same

in PCF, with the exception that the cladding has a finite number of air-holes. As a result, guided modes in PCFs are leaky by nature. In PCFs, there will be no confinement losses if and only if the cladding has an unlimited number of air-holes [37]. Theoretically, confinement losses in PCFs result from the cladding's finite size. Confinement losses can be avoided in a fiber with infinite cladding. This loss is proportional to the core size, air-hole dimension, pitch, and number of rings in the cladding. Confinement losses in PCFs are depicted in Figure 2.12. It demonstrates that the guiding light is penetrating the cladding region via the air-holes.

Figure 2.12 Confinement losses in index-guiding photonic crystal optical fibers.

2.9.5 Birefringence

PCFs have a significant variation in core shapes along the length of the fiber, which is present in real optical fibers. A fiber's cylindrical symmetry can also be destroyed when subjected to non-uniform stress.

Figure 2.13 Polarization state over one beat length in a birefringent fiber.

When the optical fibers' uniformity is broken, they acquire birefringence, resulting in periodic power exchange between the two orthogonal components. This period, as shown in Figure 2.13, is referred to as the fiber's beat length [38]. Because of this effect, a linearly polarized light remains unchanged except along the principal axes. Otherwise, the

polarization state changes along the fiber length from linear to elliptical and back to linear from elliptical over the beat length. A PM fiber is one that has intentionally added stress applying or symmetry breaking parts to a fiber so that the birefringence is no longer governed by the random core size and shape. In this case, deliberately introduced birefringence reduces the random polarization effect.

For conventional PM fibers, birefringence is typically of the order of 10^{-4} .

2.9.6 Single and Multi-mode Response

Conventional fibers can operate in either single-mode or multi-mode mode, depending on the size of the core. PCFs, on the other hand, can be designed for infinitely single-mode operation by carefully selecting air-hole dimensions and pitches. The mode diagram of IG PCFs is shown in Figure 2.14.

Figure 2.14 PCF mode diagram.

For a uniform cladding, PCFs exhibit infinitely single mode response as long as the d/Λ ratio remains within 0.45; values above this value may result in either single-mode or multimode operation. The single mode response can be calculated using the PCF's V parameter.

2.10 Conclusion

The emergence of the field of PCF, factors influencing their widespread applicability, PCF design scope and challenges in light of their application categories, and Modes of Operation It is now an important component of optical communication. Construction, light

guiding mechanisms, types, fabrication technique, and an overview of optical fiber properties and dispersion are some of the fundamental concepts of PCFs. For numerical analysis the Finite Element Method was used to extract the datas of optical properties through mode analysis.

Chapter 3

Design of slope matched hybrid photonic crystal fiber

3.1 Methodology

The first step of method of this kind of studies and research is to get realization of HyPCF waveguide which will achieve the objectives. It is very much evident that many researches conducted using the Finite Element Method as its numerical method. Though some researches also include Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) method to solve Maxwell's equations directly without any physical approximation, and the maximum problem size is limited only by the extent of the computing power available. The Finite Element Method (FEM) is used for numerically solving differential equations arising in engineering and mathematical modeling. In this research and study the waveguide has been designed by using Finite Element Method based software named COMSOL Multiphysics. After that the characteristics is investigated by using COMSOL Multiphysics. Finally the data is plotted by using high level programming language software such as MATLAB.

3.2 Numerical Method for Mode Analysis

For the accumulation of results for mode analysis a numerical method called finite element method (FEM) is used in different problems of opto-physics. This mathematical method is widely used to solve the problems in mathematical physics. In optical fiber communication the mode analysis is important to determine optical parameters. The FEM method also referred to as finite element analysis (FEA). The necessity of the method was first recognized by a German-American mathematician named Richard Courant at the start of the 1940s [41]. Structural analysis, heat transfer, electromagnetic potential, mass transport and fluid flow are some key problem areas of interest in this method. Mainly the solution to boundary value problems for partial differential equations are the analytical solution of these previously stated problems. A system of algebraic equations are the result of FEM formulation of problem. Approximate values of the unknowns at discrete number of points over the domain are yielded by this method. Basically it divides and subdivides a

large problem into smaller and simpler parts that are called finite elements for problem solving. The simpler equations are then assembled into a larger system of equations that is the design of the entire problem. Lastly FEM uses variation methods from the calculus of variations to estimate a solution by minimizing an correlated error function.

3.3 Basic concepts of FEM method

There are several advantages on subdivision of a whole domain into simpler parts:

- 1) Complex geometry can be represented with accuracy
- 2) Different material properties are included
- 3) The representation is easier of total solution
- 4) Local effects are captured.

The typical process of the methods are following-

- Splitting the full domain of the problem into a collection of subdomains, with each subsector represented by a collection of element equations to the original problem.
- For accumulating final calculations all collection of element equations are followed by systematical recombination into a global system of equations. The global system of equations particularly considered as solution techniques can be computed from the prior values of the original problem to get a numerical output.

The element equations in the first phase are simple equations that locally approximate the original complex equations to be examined, which are usually partial differential equations (PDE). FEM is typically introduced as a specific case of the Galerkin method to explain the approximation in this process. In mathematical terms, the procedure entails constructing an integral of the inner product of the residual and weight functions and setting the integral to zero. In simple terms, it's a method for reducing approximation error by fitting trial functions into the PDE. The weight functions are polynomial approximation functions that project the residual, and the residual is the error induced by the trial functions. The procedure removes all spatial derivatives from the PDE, allowing the PDE to be approximated locally using a set of algebraic equations for steady-state issues and a set of ordinary differential equations for transient problems.

The element equations are these sets of equations. If the underlying PDE is linear, they are linear, and vice versa. Ordinary differential equation sets that arise in transient problems are solved by numerical integration using standard techniques such as Euler's

method or the Runge-Kutta method. Algebraic equation sets that arise in steady state problems are solved using numerical linear algebra methods, while ordinary differential equation sets that arise in transient problems are solved by numerical integration using standard techniques such as Euler's method or the Runge-Kutta method.

Through a transfer of coordinates from the subdomains' local nodes to the domain's global nodes, a global system of equations is created from the element equations in step (2) above. In regard to the reference coordinate system, this spatial transformation includes suitable orientation corrections. FEM software is frequently used to carry out the procedure, which uses coordinate data generated by the subdomains.

The easiest way to understand FEM is to look at how it's used in practice, which is called finite element analysis (FEA). FEA is a computer tool used in engineering to undertake engineering analysis. It entails the use of mesh generation techniques for breaking down a large problem into smaller components, as well as the usage of FEM-coded software. The complex problem in FEA is typically a physical system with underlying physics such as the Euler-Bernoulli beam equation, the heat equation, or the Navier-Stokes equations expressed as PDE or integral equations, and the divided small elements of the complex problem represent different areas in the physical system.

When the domain changes (as during a solid state response with a changing border), when the necessary precision varies across the entire domain, or when the solution lacks smoothness, FEA is a viable choice. In a frontal accident simulation, for example, it is possible to improve forecast accuracy in "critical" areas like the front of the automobile while decreasing it in the back (thus reducing cost of the simulation). Another example is numerical weather prediction, where having accurate predictions over developing highly nonlinear phenomena (such as tropical cyclones in the atmosphere or eddies in the water) is more significant than having correct predictions over comparatively quiet areas.

Figure 3.1 FEM mesh output in COMSOL Multiphysics. [42]

Prior to employing FEM software to solve a magnetic problem, an analyst developed a FEM mesh. The analyst has assigned material attributes to each zone, in this case an orange conducting wire coil, a light blue ferromagnetic component (perhaps iron), and grey air. Although the design appears simple, calculating the magnetic field for this arrangement without FEM software and utilizing equations would be quite difficult.

Figure 3.2 A cylindrically formed magnetic shield is used in the FEM solution to the problem at left. By deflecting the magnetic field formed by the coil, the ferromagnetic cylindrical component shields the area inside the cylinder (rectangular area on the right). As stated by the scale in the inset legend, the color denotes the amplitude of the magnetic flux density, with red representing high amplitude. The cylinder's interior has a low amplitude (dark blue, with widely spaced lines of magnetic flux), indicating that the shield is working well.

3.4 Finite Element Method Structure

Finite element methods are numerical approaches for estimating the solutions to mathematical problems that are typically formulated to precisely express a concept of some part of physical reality. A variational formulation, a discretization approach, one or more solution algorithms, and post-processing techniques are all characteristics of a finite element method.

The Galerkin method, the discontinuous Galerkin technique, mixed methods, and other variational formulation methods are examples.

A discretization strategy is described as a series of methods that cover all aspects of a problem given below:

- a) mesh generation with finite elements
- b) the definition of reference element basis functions (also known as shape functions) and
- c) the mapping of reference elements to mesh elements. The h-version, p-version, hp-version, x-FEM, isogeometric analysis, and other discretization procedures are examples. Each discretization approach has its own set of benefits and drawbacks. The achievement of nearly optimal performance for the largest collection of mathematical models in a given model class is an acceptable criterion for selecting a discretization strategy.

There are two broad groups of numerical solution algorithms: direct and iterative solvers. These algorithms are intended to take advantage of the sparsity of matrices, which is determined by the variational formulation and discretization approach used.

The data of interest is extracted from a finite element solution using postprocessing processes. Postprocessors must give a posteriori error estimation in terms of the quantities of interest in order to meet the requirements of solution verification. When approximation errors exceed what is regarded acceptable, the discretization must be adjusted, either through an automated adaptive process or by analyst action. Super convergence can be achieved with the help of several very efficient postprocessors.

3.5 Experimental Design Procedure

The microstructure proposed is Pure silica was used as the fiber's basis material in hybrid photonic crystal fiber. In hybrid photonic crystal fiber-I (HyPCF-I), the circular air hole cladding has a hexagonal inner structure with an octagonal outer structure, and in hybrid photonic crystal fiber-II, the same inner structure with a decagonal outside structure (HyPCF-II). In the fiber cladding, only circular air holes were used along the length. A transverse cross section of the proposed fiber designs is shown in Figures 3.1 and 3.2. The artificially defective core of HyPCF-I has two hexagonal rings in the inner cladding layer and four octagonal rings in the outer cladding layer, with six air hole rings in the cladding. The inner core was tampered with by adding two smaller air holes to the first air hole ring, while the remaining four air holes remained the same as the six. The same artificial defective core was used in HyPCF-II, with five air hole rings in the cladding (two hexagonal rings in the inner cladding layer and three decagonal rings in the outer cladding layer).

Figure 3.3 Transverse cross section of proposed HyPCF-I. Where pitch, $\Lambda = 0.9 \mu\text{m}$, $d_c/\Lambda = 0.24$, $d_1/\Lambda = d_2/\Lambda = 0.94$ and $d/\Lambda = 0.7$.

Six circular air hole rings were employed in the Hybrid PCF-I design to decrease fiber confinement loss, and the defective core ring in the cladding design was used to achieve high birefringence. The smaller air holes had a diameter of $d_c = 0.22 \mu\text{m}$. The first and second ring air holes in the hexagonal construction had diameters of $d_1 = d_2 = 0.85 \mu\text{m}$. The octagonal structure's third to sixth air holes had a diameter of $d = 0.63 \mu\text{m}$. Because they had the largest influence on these properties, the two smaller first ring air holes were modified to achieve the best birefringence and dispersion solidity.

Figure 3.4 Transverse cross sectional view of proposed HyPCF-II. Where pitch, $\Lambda = 0.9$ μm , $d_c/\Lambda = 0.3$, $d_1/\Lambda = d_2/\Lambda = 0.9$ and $d/\Lambda = 0.55$.

Five circular air hole rings were engaged in the Hybrid PCF-II to decrease fiber confinement loss, and the defective core ring in the cladding design was used to achieve high birefringence. The smaller air holes had a diameter of $d_c = 0.27 \mu\text{m}$. The first and second ring air holes in the hexagonal structure had diameters of $d_1 = d_2 = 0.81 \mu\text{m}$. The decagonal structure's third to fifth air holes had a diameter of $d = 0.495 \mu\text{m}$. Because they had the largest influence on these properties, the two smaller first ring air holes were modified to achieve the best birefringence and dispersion solidity.

Figure 3.5 Transverse cross sectional view of a simple six ring hexagonal PCF. Where pitch, $\Lambda = 0.9 \mu\text{m}$ and $d/\Lambda = 0.8$.

There is another design introduced to compare the results with the proposed HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II. As the hybrid PCF structures include defected core and different cladding structures embedded in single structures so it shows some additional features than the simple structures. So, a simple six ring hexagonal PCF is presented here to compare the results and justify the proposed designs that why the hybrid defected core structures were introduced in this thesis. Six circular uniform air hole rings were involved in the hexagonal PCF to obtain some optical properties. The hexagonal structure's from first to sixth air holes had a diameter of $d = 0.72 \mu\text{m}$ while the pitch of the PCF is $0.9 \mu\text{m}$.

3.6 Design fabrication and practical realization

The pitch (Λ) of the construction is the distance between the air holes in two comparable rings. The pitch of this design was $0.9 \mu\text{m}$, which was near to $1 \mu\text{m}$, making it suitable for practical production. Drilling, sol-gel casting, tapering, and lithography [29] are only a few of the fabrication technologies that have advanced recently, therefore drawing HyPCF-I and II structures was not difficult. The sol-gel approach is currently being used to simplify the difficulty of production for any form of microstructure optical fiber, as well as PCFs with various air hole shapes and sizes [30]. The hybrid cladding looked great on this building, but the two small air holes near the core were tricky to make with the stack-and-draw method. As a result, the proposed PCF structure was created using

the sol-gel process. At a wavelength of 1550 nm, the refractive index of the fiber material (silica in this case) was $n_s = 1.45$, while the refractive index of the air holes was $n_a = 1$ at all wavelengths. Because the creation of sub-wavelength air holes with widths approximately 110 nm in the core region of silica PCF has been shown using the conventional stack-and-draw technique [32], our structure may theoretically be manufactured using the usual stack-and-draw technique [31]. The smallest air hole diameters employed in the proposed HyPCF-I and II were around 216 nm ($\approx 0.22 \mu\text{m}$) and 270 nm ($\approx 0.27 \mu\text{m}$), respectively, which is greater than previously reported, showing that the HyPCF-I and II designs can be produced utilizing the stack-and-draw process. Furthermore, with a lead silicate PCF design with air holes as tiny as 20 nm in the core region, the extrusion approach was used [33].

3.7 Conclusion

Hybrid PCF structures have a complicated approach, but if the air holes are drawn circularly and the structure remains periodic, it is simple to draw in practical manufacturing. The fiber core of the construction has two different geometrical designs. The first proposed structure, HyPCF-I, is hexagonal with an octagonal structure, while the second, HyPCF-II, is hexagonal with a decagonal structure. The main core structure of both designs is identical, with small air holes.

Chapter 4

Simulation Results and Discussions

4.1 Simulation Results

Using the COMSOL Multiphysics software, the results of two finite element technique simulations of hybrid photonic crystal structures were evaluated and shown. The optical characteristics of HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II were investigated.

4.1.1 Chromatic Dispersion

Figure 4.1(a) depicts the dispersion characteristics of x and y polarizations for optimum design parameters of $d/\Lambda = 0.7$, $d_c/\Lambda = 0.24$, $d_1/\Lambda = d_2/\Lambda = 0.94$, and pitch = 0.9 μm . The global diameter of the smaller air holes of the hexagonal cladding structure's first ring is $d_c/\Lambda = 0.24$, and the other air holes of the first and second rings are $d_1/\Lambda = d_2/\Lambda = 0.94$. The diameter parameter of the octagonal ring structure from the third to the sixth air hole rings is $d/\Lambda = 0.7$. The wavelength versus dispersion plot reveals that the proposed HyPCF-I has a negative dispersion coefficient of approximately $-358.4 \text{ ps}/(\text{nm}\cdot\text{km})$ along the y polarization at 1550 nm. In this work, the y polarization dispersion is considered to be the optimum value of dispersion.

Figure 4.1(b) displays the x and y polarization dispersion characteristics with optimum design parameters of $d/\Lambda = 0.55$, $d_c/\Lambda = 0.3$, $d_1/\Lambda = d_2/\Lambda = 0.9$, and pitch = 0.9 μm . The smaller air holes in the first ring of the hexagonal cladding structure have a global diameter of $d_c/\Lambda = 0.3$, while the other air holes in the first and second rings have a global diameter of $d_1/\Lambda = d_2/\Lambda = 0.9$. The diameter parameter of the decagonal ring structure from the third to the fifth air hole rings is $d/\Lambda = 0.55$. The plot of wavelength versus dispersion shows that the proposed HyPCF-II exhibits ultra-high negative dispersion coefficient of y polarization at 1550 nm, which is about $-3534 \text{ ps}/(\text{nm}\cdot\text{km})$. In this work, the y polarization dispersion is considered to be the optimum value of dispersion. Because of their high negative dispersion coefficient, the proposed HyPCFs may be a good candidate for dispersion compensation in high bit rate transmission networks.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.1 Wavelength dependence dispersion curve for both x and y polarization of (a) HyPCF-I and (b) HyPCF-II.

During fabrication, a $\pm 1\%$ variation in global diameters may be followed in PCF. As a result, we evaluated the effect on dispersion and birefringence by varying different parameters ranging from $\pm 1\%$ to $\pm 2\%$, as briefly argued in the following section.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.2 Effect on dispersion vs. wavelength by changing pitch value of (a) HyPCF-I and (b) HyPCF-II.

Figures 4.2 (a) and (b) show the effect of varying the global diameter of pitch by $\pm 1\%$ to $\pm 2\%$ while keeping the other parameters constant. The solid line represents an increase in parameters, while the dashed line represents a decrease in parameters. When pitch is varied from $\pm 1\%$ to $\pm 2\%$, the corresponding dispersion value of HyPCF-I is -372.7 , -365.5 , -351.2 , and -344 ps/(nm.km), respectively. Again, when pitch is varied from $\pm 1\%$

to $\pm 2\%$, the corresponding dispersion value of HyPCF-II is -3675 , -3605 , -3463 , and -3393 ps/(nm.km), respectively.

A PCF with extremely high negative dispersion is preferable for long-distance optical communication. Because it has less pulse boarding and pulse spreading. Although negative dispersion PCF models have been discovered, there are still gaps in their development. To meet the demand for dispersion profiles in optical communication, ultra-high negative dispersion is highly recommended.

4.1.2 Birefringence

The fiber birefringence reflects the ability to maintain polarization, and a high birefringence can improve the accuracy and stability of the system.

Figure 4.3 depicts the birefringence properties of these proposed HyPCF designs. This feature of the proposed HyPCF-I and II design will enable sensing applications [39]. The reported fiber core design's uneven design exposes high birefringence, which is required for polarization retaining applications. Existing typical polarization preserving fibers, on the other hand, showed modal birefringence of roughly 5×10^{-4} [40].

Furthermore, at optimum design parameters, the HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II display birefringence of roughly 3.04×10^{-2} and 2.372×10^{-2} , respectively, suggesting that they could be ideal candidates for sensing applications. The impact on pitch in HyPCF-I birefringence is also computed in figure 4.3(a).

Birefringence at 1550 nm is 0.03008, 0.03069, 0.02978, and 0.03099, respectively, as the value of pitch is altered by $\pm 1\%$ to $\pm 2\%$ from its ideal value. Figure 4.3(b) shows that the variation in birefringence of HyPCF-II at 1550 nm changed by 0.02324, 0.02348, 0.02395, and 0.02419, respectively, while pitch changed by $\pm 1\%$ to $\pm 2\%$.

The proposed high birefringence HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II may find important applications in optical fiber communications, fiber lasers, and fiber sensors, and the added negative dispersion feature makes it suitable as a chromatic dispersion controller, a dispersion compensator, or a candidate for nonlinear optical applications.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.3 Wavelength versus birefringence plot of (a) HyPCF-I and (b) HyPCF-II for optimum design parameters with variation of pitch from $\pm 1\%$ to $\pm 2\%$.

4.1.3 Nonlinearity and Effective area

Figure 4.4(a) shows that the optimal effective area values for the HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II at 1550 nm were $2.766 \mu\text{m}^2$ and $2.236 \mu\text{m}^2$, respectively. Figure 6.4 depicts the

nonlinearity plot of the reported HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II for optimum pitch of the design parameters (b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.4 (a) Effective area versus wavelength curve and (b) Non-linear coefficient versus wavelength curve of proposed HyPCF-I and II for optimum design parameters.

At 1550 nm operating wavelength, the measures of nonlinearity at optimum pitch value were $42.35 \text{ W}^{-1} \text{ km}^{-1}$ and $52.38 \text{ W}^{-1} \text{ km}^{-1}$, respectively. According to the results, the

proposed designs of HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II have a good effective area and nonlinearity for use in nonlinear applications.

4.1.4 Single Mode Performance

Because fiber may have higher order modes (HOMs), the single mode performance of our proposed HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II fiber were examined in this section. If the HOMs losses are significantly greater than the fundamental mode (FM) loss, the fiber can be adequately operated as a single mode fiber. It was tried to compute the higher order mode extinction ratio (HOMER), which can indicate the light leakage loss of HOMs in comparison to the leakage loss of fundamental mode. The loss of the first six core modes (fundamental and HOMs) is observed, which are HE_{11} , TE_{01} , TM_{01} , HE_{21} , EH_{11} , and HE_{31} [52]. Figure 4.5 illustrates the field distribution of different higher order modes analyzed for x and y polarization scenario.

Figure 4.5 Fundamental and higher order modes (HOMs) field distribution with its directions for proposed HyPCF-I.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.6 (a) The loss performance of proposed fiber HYPCF-I (loss of fundamental and HOMs) as a function of wavelength, and (b) HOMER versus wavelength of HyPCF-I for x polarization. Here, TM_{01} shows the lowest loss among all HOMs. The frame color of each picture of x polarization modes correlates with the line color of loss curve in Figure 4.5.

The confinement loss of the first six core modes as a function of wavelength for HyPCF-I for x polarization is shown in Figure 4.6(a). The loss of FMs such as HE_{11}

reaches 0.01791dB/m at 1550 nm operating wavelength. The loss of HOMs for x polarization (TE_{01} , TM_{01} , HE_{21} , EH_{11} , and HE_{31}) reaches respectively 1.128×10^5 , 4.839×10^4 , 5.772×10^4 , 6.158×10^4 , 7.664×10^4 dB/m at 1550 nm operating wavelength. When the losses from the graph were compared at the optimum frequency of 1550 nm, which is in the communication band, the confinement loss of TM_{01} was found to be lower than the other higher order modes. Also it is evident that in the S+C+L communication bands the HOMs loss varies from 10^4 to 10^5 order ranges but for fundamental mode it increases from 10^{-5} to 10^{-1} order ranges. The goal of each work is to keep the HOMER at or above 10 over a broadband connection in order to maintain acceptable single mode performance [53]. The proposed work HyPCF-I also attempts to achieve the highest possible HOMER over a wide wavelength range. As illustrated in Figure 4.6(b), the highest HOMER of HyPCF-I for x polarizat on at 1550 nm operating wavelength found around 10^6 and remains greater than 100 over both communication windows [54].

The confinement loss of the first six core modes as a function of wavelength for HyPCF-I for y polarization is shown in Figure 4.7(a). The loss of FMs for y polarization such as HE_{11} achieves 1.122 dB/m at 1550 nm operating wavelength. The loss of HOMs for y polarization (TE_{01} , TM_{01} , HE_{21} , EH_{11} , and HE_{31}) attains respectively 1.128×10^5 , 4.839×10^4 , 7.09×10^4 , 6.035×10^4 , 9.432×10^4 dB/m at 1550 nm operating wavelength.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.7 (a) The loss performance of proposed fiber HYPCF-I (loss of fundamental and HOMs) as a function of wavelength, and (b) HOMER versus wavelength of HyPCF-I for y polarization. Here, TM_{01} shows the lowest loss among all HOMs. The frame color of each picture of y polarization modes correlates with the line color of loss curve in Figure 4.5.

(c) HE_{11} x-polarization

(d) HE_{11} y-polarization

(c) HE_{21} x-polarization

(d) HE_{21} y-polarization

(e) HE_{31} x-polarization

(f) HE_{31} y-polarization

(g) EH₁₁ x-polarization

(h) EH₁₁ y-polarization

(k) TE₀₁

(l) TM₀₁

Figure 4.8 Fundamental and higher order modes (HOMs) field distribution with its directions for proposed HyPCF-II.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.9 (a) The loss performance of proposed fiber HYPCF-II (loss of fundamental and HOMs) as a function of wavelength, and (b) HOMER versus wavelength of HyPCF-II for x polarization. Here, TM_{01} shows the lowest loss among all HOMs. The frame color of each picture of x polarization modes correlates with the line color of loss curve in Figure 4.8.

4.8.

The confinement loss of the first six core modes as a function of wavelength for HyPCF-II for x polarization is shown in Figure 4.9(a). The loss of FMs such as HE_{11} reaches 3.071dB/m at 1550 nm operating wavelength. The loss of HOMs (TE_{01} , TM_{01} , HE_{21} , EH_{11} , and HE_{31}) reaches respectively 4.66×10^4 , 2.884×10^3 , 5.802×10^3 , 3.717×10^3 , 8.405×10^3 dB/m at 1550 nm operating wavelength. When the losses from the graph were compared at the operating wavelength of 1550 nm, which is in the communication band, the confinement loss of TM_{01} was found to be lower than the other higher order modes. Also it is evident that in the S+C+L communication bands the HOMs loss varies from 10^3 to 10^4 order ranges but for fundamental mode it increases from 10^{-2} to 10 order ranges.

As illustrated in Figure 4.9(b), the highest HOMER of HyPCF-II at 1550 nm operating wavelength found around 10^4 and remains greater than 100 over both communication windows.

The confinement loss of the first six core modes as a function of wavelength for HyPCF-II is shown in Figure 4.10(a) for y polarization. The loss of FMs such as HE_{11} reaches 3.96×10^2 dB/m at 1550 nm operating wavelength. The loss of HOMs (TE_{01} , TM_{01} , HE_{21} , EH_{11} , and HE_{31}) reaches respectively 4.66×10^4 , 2.884×10^3 , 5.084×10^3 , 2.67×10^3 , 9.786×10^3 dB/m at 1550 nm operating wavelength. When the losses from the graph were compared at the operating wavelength of 1550 nm, which is in the communication band, the confinement loss of EH_{11} was found to be lower than the other higher order modes. Also it is evident that in the S+C+L communication bands the HOMs loss varies from 10^3 to 10^4 order ranges but for fundamental mode it increases from 10^{-1} to 10^3 order ranges.

The goal of each work is to keep the HOMER at or above 10 over a broadband connection in order to maintain acceptable single mode performance. The proposed work HyPCF-II also attempts to achieve the highest possible HOMER over a wide wavelength range. As illustrated in Figure 4.9(b), the highest HOMER of HyPCF-II at 1550 nm operating wavelength found around 10^3 and remains greater than 100 over both communication windows.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.10 (a) The loss performance of proposed fiber HYPCF-II (loss of fundamental and HOMs) as a function of wavelength, and (b) HOMER versus wavelength of HyPCF-II for y polarization. Here, EH_{11} shows the lowest loss among all HOMs. The frame color of each picture of y polarization modes correlates with the line color of loss curve in Figure 4.8.

4.8.

4.1.5 Residual Dispersion Slope Matching

For residual dispersion slope matching the x -polarization dispersion compensation outcomes of the proposed PCFs are considered. The residual dispersion occurs when an optical fiber carries data through a long distance. After a long distance there is some dispersion residue in the transmission waveguide channel. So compensating this dispersion is very important in long distance WDM communication systems. Also the residual dispersion slope indicates a fiber is how much closer to the characteristics of a single mode fiber. Figure 4.11 shows that the RDS values of our proposed HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II are 0.003623nm^{-1} and 0.003491nm^{-1} , respectively, which correspond to the RDS slope of single mode fibers. To achieve better dispersion compensation, the RDS of single mode fiber must be matched. The proposed HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II effective dispersion curves shown in figure 4.12 are nearly zero dispersion flattened, with values of flattened dispersion coefficients of -0.7715 ± 0.95945 ps/(nm.km) and 1.16415 ± 1.97985 ps/(nm.km) within the 300 nm flat band ranging from 1400 nm to 1700 nm. Figure 4.13 also examines the compensation ratio (CR) of fiber dispersion to demonstrate the achievement of flattened dispersion at wavelengths ranging from 1400 nm to 1700 nm. The residual dispersion versus wavelength plot is shown in figure 4.14 after compensating for dispersion through 1 km long suggested HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II, which is equal to the total dispersion in 50 km long SMF. The residual dispersion of HyPCF-I is close to zero in the 1450 nm to 1650 nm wavelength band. Analyzing the results, it is clear that this HyPCF-I design could be a suitable candidate for high bit-rate transmission systems across the range of interests.

Figure 4.11 Wavelength dependent relative dispersion slope (RDS) curve of the proposed HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II after compensating for 50 km long SMFs.

Figure 4.12 Wavelength dependent effective dispersion curve of the proposed HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II after compensating for 50 km long SMFs.

Figure 4.13 Wavelength versus dispersion compensation ratio curve of the proposed HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II after compensating for 50 km long SMFs.

Figure 4.14 Wavelength versus residual dispersion curve of the proposed HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II after compensating for 50 km long SMFs.

4.1.6 Confinement loss

The losses caused by the leaky nature of the modes and the non-perfect structure of the PCF fiber are referred to as confinement losses. Modes will then be guided with a structure dependent loss depending on the wavelength, number of air hole rings, and air hole size.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.15 Confinement loss versus wavelength curve with optimum design parameters for x polarization and y polarization of (a) HyPCF-I and (b) HyPCF-II.

Both x and y polarization confinement losses have been analyzed for HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II designs. Figures 4.15(a) and (b) show the observation of optimal confinement loss with respect to wavelength for x polarization and y polarization reported HyPCF-I and II (b). According to the plot, the optimum value of confinement loss for x polarization at 1550 nm wavelength is 0.01791 dB/m. The optimum value of confinement loss for y

polarization at 1550 nm wavelength is 1.122 dB/m. At the operating wavelength, the optimum confinement loss value of HyPCF-II x polarization and y polarization is 3.071 dB/m and 6.809×10^2 dB/m respectively. The graph clearly shows that the confinement loss increases with increasing wavelength. This trend of the graph exposed that due to the fundamental field distribution of the proposed PCFs increased with respect to wavelength, the leaky nature of the mode also increased. Same reason is also applicable to the fact that the confinement loss of x polarization is lesser than that of y polarization.

4.2 Fundamental Field distribution

Figures 4.16 (a) and (b) show the spreading of the fundamental optical field for x and y polarization modes for HyPCF-I at an effective wavelength of 1550 nm. Figures 4.16 (c) and (d) show the spreading of the fundamental optical field for x and y polarization modes for HyPCF-II at an effective wavelength of 1550 nm.

According to simulation results, modes in x and y polarization are firmly bounded at the center core area due to higher index availability in the center than in the cladding.

Figure 4.16 Fundamental field distribution modes for (a) x -polarization and (b) y -polarization for HyPCF-I and (c) x -polarization and (d) y -polarization for HyPCF-II at effective wavelength.

4.3 Comparison of optical properties between other PCF's

Dispersion compensation over the S, C, and L bands of telecommunication is validated in the residual dispersion curve by matching the residual dispersion slope of the described HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II. The suggested HyPCF-I and II will have a major real-world applicability in communication applications and optical sensing. Finally, a comparison is made between the HyPCF-I & II and other fibers previously explored for dispersion compensation and sensing applications in terms of birefringence and residual dispersion characteristics. The evaluation of these optical qualities is shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Optical Property Comparison of Suggested HyPCFs and Other PCFs

PCFs	Cladding Structure	Dispersion, $D(\lambda)$ [ps/(nm.km)]	Birefringence, $B= n_x-n_y $	Confinement loss, L_c (dB/m)	RDS (nm^{-1})
Ref. [12]	Octagonal	- 588	1.81×10^{-2}	< 10	--
Ref. [13]	Octagonal	- 239.51	1.67×10^{-2}	3.2×10^{-5}	0.0034
Ref. [14]	Spiral	- 400	1.60×10^{-2}	--	--
Ref. [16]	Defected core Circular	- 331	2.75×10^{-2}	--	0.0036
Ref. [17]	Square-core Octagonal	- 294.1	2.13×10^{-2}	0.42	0.0036
Ref. [19]	Elliptical air hole Hexagonal	- 156 ± 0.5	1.94×10^{-2}	10^{-4}	--
Ref. [20]	Asymmetric core Circular	- 345	2.78×10^{-2}	< 10^{-2}	0.0036
Proposed HyPCF-I	Defected core Hybrid (Hexagonal- Octagonal)	- 358.4	3.039×10^{-2}	1.791×10^{-2}	0.0036
Proposed HyPCF-II	Defected core Hybrid (Hexagonal- Decagonal)	- 3534	2.372×10^{-2}	3.071	0.0034

4.4 Reason of using Hybrid Structure

For the justification of using the hybrid structures instead of normal sequential structures a simple hexagonal photonic crystal fiber design is introduced. The simple hexagonal photonic crystal fiber design was designed with optimal parameters. After the simulation using finite element method some optical parameters were revealed with respect to wavelengths between communication bands.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.17 Wavelength versus Chromatic Dispersion plot for (a) x-polarization and (b) y-polarization fundamental modes of simple hexagonal PCF design.

First of all the chromatic dispersion properties were analyzed for both x and y polarization fundamental modes. In figure 4.17(a) the wavelength versus chromatic dispersion plot is shown. The value of chromatic dispersion at 1550 nm operating wavelength is -550.088 ps/(nm.km) for x polarization. Figure 4.17(b) demonstrates the wavelength dependent chromatic dispersion curve for y polarization modes. The chromatic dispersion found at 1550 nm operating wavelength is -549.916 ps/(nm.km) for y polarization. There is a slight change in the negative dispersion for both the polarizations but the defected core hybrid structures exhibits a drastically change for both polarizations. The simple hexagonal structure also shows negative dispersion in the communication band but the HyPCF-II (hybrid) structure supersedes in this matter.

Now observing the birefringence property of the simple hexagonal structure the value of birefringence is found 2.17×10^{-7} at 1550 nm wavelength. The figure 4.18 shows the wavelength versus birefringence curve for simple hexagonal structure. The birefringence value is very low which is at the order of 10^{-7} . So, this structure is not suitable for polarization maintaining optical properties, sensing applications and fiber loop mirroring type of applications. But the defected core parts of the hybrid cladding structures successfully maintain the birefringence value at the order of 10^{-2} which is higher and better than the simple structure.

Figure 4.18 Wavelength dependent birefringence curve of a simple hexagonal PCF structure.

Figure 4.19 Wavelength dependent confinement loss curve of a simple hexagonal PCF structure.

In figure 4.19 the wavelength versus confinement loss curve was demonstrated. The curve trends as the wavelength increases the confinement loss also increased. At 1550 nm wavelength the confinement loss found 1.237×10^{-5} dB/m which is quite satisfactory. Because of the adjacent air holes are very close to each other and the structure is symmetric in nature so the confinement loss is low in the operating wavelength.

Figure 4.20 Wavelength dependent relative dispersion slope (RDS) curve of the simple hexagonal cladding structure PCF after compensating for 50 km long SMFs.

For residual dispersion slope matching test after compensating for 50 km long single mode fiber the optimum value of the relative dispersion slope (RDS) is 0.002371 nm^{-1} at 1550 nm wavelength. The wavelength dependent RDS curve has been demonstrated in figure 4.20. The RDS value for this particular structure did not match with the standard value for a single mode fiber.

Despite of having a good confinement loss property the simple hexagonal cladding PCF structure has failed to achieve the residual dispersion slope matching and higher birefringence property. But the proposed defected core hybrid cladding structures achieve these properties with a good note.

4.5 Conclusion

At the reference wavelength of 1550 nm, the simulation results of the hybrid PCF's optical properties were plotted and examined. The birefringence of the HyPCF-I structure is higher than that of the HyPCF-II structure. In comparison to HyPCF-I, HyPCF-II has a higher negative dispersion value. The importance of using defected core hybrid cladding structure was also discussed in this chapter by comparing the optical properties of a simple hexagonal PCF structure.

Chapter 5

Concluding Remarks and Future Recommendations

5.1 Conclusions

The proposed artificially defected core hybrid photonic crystal fiber designs exhibit high birefringence and nonlinearity, which makes them suitable for use as an optical sensor. In order to achieve dispersion-compensating applications, this design achieves a dispersion coefficient with a high negative value. The stated HyPCF-I achieves 3.04×10^{-2} as high birefringence and $42.35 \text{W}^{-1} \text{km}^{-1}$ as highly nonlinear quantity at the effective wavelength of 1550 nm, recommending it as a good candidate for an optical sensor. Within the S, C, and L communication bands, the simulation results show a zero flattened residual dispersion of $-0.7715 \pm 0.95945 \text{ ps}/(\text{nm} \cdot \text{km})$. Because of its excellent guiding properties, this fiber design can be used for other optical sensing and wideband dispersion compensation at high bit stream rates in wavelength division multiplexing transmission systems. The second modified structure of photonic crystal fiber, denoted as HyPCF-II, on the other hand, achieves higher negative dispersion than HyPCF-I. At 1550 nm effective wavelength, the negative dispersion coefficient of HyPCF-II is $-3534 \text{ ps}/(\text{nm} \cdot \text{km})$, which is higher than the negative dispersion coefficient of HyPCF-I $-358.4 \text{ ps}/(\text{nm} \cdot \text{km})$ of HyPCF-I. When the x polarization dispersion is taken into account, both structures show residual dispersion slope matching at 0.0036 nm^{-1} . The first structure meets the benchmark of single-mode residual dispersion slope at the operating wavelength, whereas the second structure came close (0.0034 nm^{-1}) to it. The birefringence of HyPCF-II is 2.372×10^{-2} lower than that of HyPCF-I. HyPCF-II has a nonlinearity of $52.38 \text{W}^{-1} \text{km}^{-1}$ at 1550 nm, making it suitable for supercontinuum generation applications. Also for single mode operation for both designs the HOMER were found 10^6 and 10^4 respectively for HyPCF-I and HyPCF-II proposed structures.

5.2 Future Recommendations

Because it is a periodic structure and flexible in designing optical waveguides, there are numerous possibilities for designing microstructure PCF structures. Some recommendations are given below:

- More complex structures can now be fabricated in small spaces thanks to recent advances in nanofabrication methodology.
- The confinement loss is one of the main drawbacks of PCF structures, so suitable designs that reduce the loss are important from this standpoint.
- Long-distance communication systems benefit from slope matching PCFs.
- Highly nonlinear PCFs could have been a better option in supercontinuum generation if they had this property. The generation of supercontinuum is widely used in the design of high contrast optical amplifiers.
- Nonlinear optics and terahertz transmission systems are on the horizon in the future.
- Highly negatively flatten dispersion will aid in data transmission over a wide range of spectrum.
- The high birefringence is advantageous in sensing applications.
- However, it is also critical to achieve a large mode area for telecommunication. Future designs should take this into account as well.

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